

MICROWAVE ACTIVATED SHAPE MEMORY POLYMER

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ABSTRACT

In this paper the tetra-needle-shaped zinc oxide whisker (T-ZnO_w) was filled in the shape memory polymer (SMP) with different weight fraction and the T-ZnO_w/SMP composite obtained the ability of microwave absorption while maintaining the basic thermal mechanical properties and shape memory characteristics. The absorbed microwave energy could be transferred into heat efficiently in the T-ZnO_w/SMP composite and the remote actuation of complex shape transitions by microwave is possible.

1 General Introduction

Shape memory polymers possess the ability to memorize a permanent shape that can substantially differ from their initial temporary shape. Large bulky device could thus potentially be introduced into the body in a compressed temporary shape by means of minimally invasive surgery and then be expended on demand to their permanent shape to fit as required. The transition from the temporary shape to permanent shape could be initiated by an external stimulus, increasing the temperature to the transition point is the common way to activate the shape memory effect. Since the device used in minimally invasive surgery is very small and should be activated in body, how to initial the shape transition effectively and conveniently is one of the key problems to the clinic operation. Several ways to activate the SMP device have already been reported. Jinsong Leng *et al* [5] obtained conductive SMP by mixing some conductive material such as carbon blacks, carbon nanotubes and short carbon fibers. Upon application of an electrical current, the temperature is increased as a result of the high ohmic resistance of this kind of composite. Géraldine M Baer, *et al* [1] and Small *et al* [2] developed a way to activate the shape memory polymer vascular stent and shape memory polymer intravascular thrombectomy device by laser. The laser was introduced and coupled into SMP by an optical fiber and the light was transferred to heat because of the photo-thermo effect. The fact that a direct contact to the SMP device by electrodes is necessary in the named examples strongly restricts the use of these systems in biological environments.

Annette M, *et al* [3] and Nanda Gopal Sahoo, *et al* [4] described the synthesis and properties of special SMP composites by incorporation of magnetic nanoparticles into shape-memory thermoplastics and the remote actuation of the thermally induced shape-memory effect was realized by applying an alternating magnetic field respectively. Compare with those with the contact electrodes, the remote stimulation is much more convenient. In this paper, another way to activate the shape memory composite remotely was

realized. By mixing with T-ZnO_w particles, which can absorb microwaves because of its special microstructure, T-ZnO_w/SMP composite obtained the ability of microwave absorption while maintaining the shape memory properties. The absorbed microwave energy could be transferred into heat efficiently so as to active the shape memory effect of the device made of the T-ZnO_w/SMP composite. The heating efficiency and the heating homogeneity were determined by the content fraction and the desparation of the T-ZnO_w particles in the composite. Compare with the magnetic — nanoparticles/SMP composites, which could be activated by a 5.0 KW commercial HF generator[2], the T-ZnO_w /SMP obtained in this paper could be heated and activated by a 100W microwave, which means that the way to activate the shape memory device introduced in this paper is easier and safer than that described in [3] and [4].

2 MATERIL AND METHODS

2.1 SAMPLES PREPARATION

The T-ZnO_w (5.96 g/cm³) was purchased from Jing Yu Corporation in China. The length of each needle of T-ZnO_w is about 10~20 μm, and the diameter of each needle at the growth point is about 1~5μm. The tensile strength and elastic modulus are $10^4 Mpa$ and $3.5 \times 10^4 Mpa$ respectively. All the material parameters mentioned above were provided by the production corporations.

To prepare the composite specimens, the T-ZnO_w was put into the acetone coupling agents little by little and dispersed for 2 hours by ultrasonic vibration. The SMP resin and the hardener were mixed with the weight ratio of 10:4, the dispersed T-ZnO_w was mixed into the SMP mixture and the whole mixture was stirred fully and then was cast into a stainless steel model and cured for 24 hours in room temperature. Be sure mixing the mixture gently in case to break the micro needles in T-ZnO_w. Five types of the specimens were prepared with the different content ratio of T-ZnO_w, which were 10%, 20%, 30%,40% and 50%.wt. The pure SMP specimens were also prepared.

2.2 THE TEST OF TRABSITION TEMPERATURE

The Young's modulus of the T-ZnO_w /SMP at the different temperature was tested at an Instoron universal test instrument with a temperature controlled chamber by direct tension.

2.3 The test of recovery strain and recovery stress

The shape memory characters of T-ZnO_w /SMP composite were examined by the shape fixity, shape recovery ratio and shape recovery stress. There were three steps to investigate the fixity and shape recovery properties. (1) The spacemen was tensioned to certain strain level ε_m at higher temperature $T_h > T_g$ by the test machine. (2) The specimen was cooled to the low temperature $T_l < T_g$ while maintain the tensioned strain, kept for 10 minutes and then

unloaded, where small unloading strain ε_u occurred and the most of the strain $\varepsilon_f = \varepsilon_m - \varepsilon_u$ was fixed. The fixed strain was measured as the index of shape fixity property of T-ZnO_w/SMP composite. (3) Then the specimen was heated again from T_l to T_h under unload state and the recovered strain was measured as the index of shape recovery property. There were also three steps to test the recovery stress, the first and second steps were similar to that in recovery strain test. However in the third step, the recovery strain was constrained and the recovery stress was measured with a load cell when the specimen was heated again in temporary shape.

2.3 The microwave absorption heating transformation measurement

To test the microwave absorption and heating transformation ability in T-ZnO_w /SMP, the rectangular plant specimens with different T-ZnO_w fraction were exposed to microwave radiation generated by a medicine microwave curing machine operated at 3.3Gz with a power of 100w respectively .The temperature on the surface of the specimens was measured with a hand infrared radiation thermometer. The temperature was recorded by hand for every 5 second.

To test the effectiveness of the shape memory initiation by the low power microwave, two rectangular strip specimens with the dimension of $20 \times 5 \times 2\text{mm}$, one with 40% .wt. T-ZnO_w ratio and the other with none , were used. The specimens were rolled up at the temperature of 50°C which was higher then glass transition temperature T_g and then cooled down in cool water to keep the temporary shape. After this programming process, the specimens kept the helical shape in the absence of external forces as can be seen in Figure 2b(0S). The two specimens were exposed to microwave as described above. The shape transition was recorded with a digital camera and the temperature on the surface of the specimens was measured with a hand infrared radiation thermometer.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 the transation temperature

The schema of Yong's modulus — temperature curves for two kinds of composite with two T-ZnO_w weight fraction and SMP bulk were shown in Fig.1. It was obviously that the Young's modulus increased with the T-ZnO_w fraction while the glass transition temperature T_g decreased.

For the composite with the 20% T-ZnO_w weight fraction, the glass transition temperature was about 32°C and for the 10% T-ZnO_w weight fraction composite the T_g was about 36°C while the

T_g of the pure SMP was about 38 °C.

Figure 1: The transition temperature with different ZnO_w

3.1 The strain recovery ratio and recovery stress

Fig.4 showed the recovery strain at different stretched ratio with the different T-ZnO_w fraction. It can be seen that the mixture of the T-ZnO_w influence the shape recovery ability slightly, especially for the lower T-ZnO_w fraction this influence could be ignored. The relationship between the recovery stress and the T-ZnO_w fraction was shown in figure 5.

It is clear that the recovery stress increased with the T-ZnO_w fraction when the T-ZnO_w .wt.%<30%. However, when T-ZnO_w exceed a specified amount, since the interaction carry out between T-ZnO_w and shape memory polymer and also between T-ZnO_w particles, the internal stored elastic strain energy may waste so the recovery stress decreases. From the above experimental and analyse results it can be conclude that the T-ZnO_w /SMP maintain the shape memory prosperities.

Figure 2: The strain recovery ratio var stretch strain for different T-Zno_w fraction

Figure 3: The recovery stress var T-ZnO_w fraciom

Figure 4: The average temperature on the surface of T-ZnO_w /SMP bulk

The average temperatures on the surface of the T-ZnO_w /SMP sample with the exposing time were shown in Figure 4. For the pure SMP sample, the temperature changes slightly during the whole exposing time. For the T-ZnO_w /SMP composite plants, the temperature increasing speed got quickly with the increasing of T-ZnO_w fraction.

In Figure 5, the photo series documents the microwave activated shape memory effect of ZnO_w/SMP sample. After 20 seconds, the starting conversion of the ZnO_w/SMP helix was observed and taking another 10 s to be completed, the temperature increased from room temperature (22°C, below T_g) to 42°C(above T_g) at the same time while the reference specimen remained the helix shape and the temperature had no obviously change.

Figure 5: The photo series of curved SMP samples under the microwave

4 CONCLUSIONS

It has been demonstrated that by the incorporation of T-ZnOw particles in a shape memory polymer matrix, it is possible to initiate an originally thermally activated shape memory effects by a touchless and highly selective microwave stimulus, while the basic materials properties in terms of thermal and mechanical behavior are maintained. The novel materials are of interest for medical applications as well as in sensor and actuator systems.

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